

A Review of Our Recent Studies on Mechanisms of Reactions of Metal Complexes

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THE different types of reactions of metal complexes on which mechanistic studies have been carried out recently in the author's laboratory during the last 10 years may be broadly classified as follows : (1) Formation of metal complexes involving replacement of aqua ligand. (2) Aquation and base hydrolysis of acido-ammine complexes. (3) Replacement of mono- and bi-dentate ligands by the poly-dentate ligand, EDTA. (4) Dissociation of metal chelates : Nucleophilic and electrophilic catalysis. (5) Electron transfer reactions. The significant results are briefly reported below.

1. Formation of metal complexes involving replacement of aqua ligand.

The formation of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_4(\text{AA})^+$ (AA = oxalate¹, malonate²) from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_6^{3+}$ and the protonated ligands in acid solution has been studied. ΔH^\ddagger values for these reactions are comparable to that for the water exchange reaction of the hexaquo-chromium(III) ion and the results are consistent with a mechanism in which there is outer-sphere association between the reacting species followed by transformation of the outer-sphere complexes into the products by an essentially dissociative process ($S_{\text{N}}1$ IP mechanism). For the reaction of the hexaquo ion with glycine, however, the ΔH^\ddagger value is only 12.4 kcal mole⁻¹ as against 26.1 kcal mole⁻¹ for the water exchange reaction³. Outer-sphere association has been inferred from spectrophotometric observations in the UV region and the results are consistent with $S_{\text{N}}2$ IP mechanism⁴.

Formation of $\text{cis-Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_2(\text{AA})_2^-$ (AA = oxalate⁵, malonate⁶) from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_4(\text{AA})^+$ has also been studied. Reactions occur through outer-sphere association, but high ΔH^\ddagger value (23.9 kcal mole⁻¹ in the case of oxalate and 24.8 kcal mole⁻¹ in the case of malonate) comparable to reactions of several other

chromium(III) complexes primarily involving $\text{Cr}(\text{III})\text{-OH}_2$ bond rupture in the transition state indicates $S_{\text{N}}1$ IP mechanism.

Formation of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{2+}$ ($\text{X}^- = \text{OAc}^-$, N_3^-) from $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH}_2)^{3+}$ has been studied. The acetato complex is formed by concurrent $S_{\text{N}}1$ and $S_{\text{N}}1$ IP paths from the aquo complex⁷. Analysis of the observed dependences of rate on pH and azide concentration shows that both the aquo complex and its conjugate base, $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$, react with azide⁸. ΔH^\ddagger value for the reaction of the aquo complex with azide ion is comparable to the corresponding value⁹ for the anation of the aquo complex by Cl^- and NCS^- . The mechanism thus appears to be dissociative ($S_{\text{N}}1$ IP). The reaction of the hydroxo complex probably occurs by a similar mechanism and in agreement with this the ΔH^\ddagger value for this reaction is ca. 7 kcal mole⁻¹ higher than the corresponding reaction of the aquo complex in keeping with the higher energy expected for the rupture of $\text{Cr}(\text{III})\text{-OH}$ bond compared to $\text{Cr}(\text{III})\text{-OH}_2$ bond. Based on the k_1/k_{ex} values (where k_1 and k_{ex} represent the rate constants for reaction with the ligand and that for water exchange respectively under comparable conditions) the following order of nucleophilicity of some ligands towards $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5^{3+}$ has been derived (using literature values for the NCS^- and Cl^- ; ref. 9) : $\text{N}_3^- > \text{NCS}^- > \text{Cl}^-$, which is identical to that of these ions towards Ph_3C^+ and of NCS^- and N_3^- towards $\text{Co}(\text{CN})_5^{2-}$ as described in literature.

Formation of $\text{Cr}(\text{Ox})_2(\text{AA})^-$ (AA = phen, dipyl) from $\text{cis-Cr}(\text{Ox})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2^-$ has been studied recently¹⁰. There are two concurrent paths, one independent of reagent (AA) and another showing first order dependence on reagent concentration; the rate constant, k_3 , for the former being almost identical to that for

the water exchange reaction of the cis-diaquo-bis-oxalato complex under comparable conditions.

Results (k_o independent of AA, $k_{AA}/k_o \approx 10^2$, $\Delta H^\ddagger (k_{AA})/\Delta H^\ddagger (k_o) \approx 1.75$) indicate dissociative mechanism for the reagent independent path (k_o) and displacement mechanism for the reagent dependent path (k_{AA}), the latter involving simultaneous rupture of two Cr(III)-OH₂ bonds as the steric requirements in case of phenanthroline at least would predict where both nitrogen donors must be bonded simultaneously to the metal.

In the formation of Cr(BigH)₂(OX)⁺ from Cr(BigH)₂(OH₂)₂³⁺ (where BigH = biguanide) and oxalic acid in weakly acidic solutions¹¹ the rate shows a first order dependence on total oxalate concentration and is independent of pH in the range 3-4 although the relative proportions of OX²⁻ and HOX⁻ ions vary considerably within this region. These results indicate that both the ions are virtually equally reactive through formation of ion-pairs with the cationic substrate. It, therefore, follows that the ion-pair formation constants for both are nearly equal which is not unlikely since the oxalate ion ⁻OOC.COO⁻ may be oriented in the ion-pair with one COO⁻ end pointing towards the cationic complex and hence the situation would not be very different from that in the case of HOX⁻. Also, association in these cases may be predominantly due to hydrogen bonding interaction between an aqua ligand in the complex and the oxalate ions. The ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values are comparable to those for reactions of several complexes of Cr(III) which involve rupture of Cr(III)-OH₂ bond. This suggests that in all these cases rupture of Cr(III)-OH₂ bond is primarily important in the transition state and hence the mechanism is S_N1 IP.

Formation of Co(NH₃)₅(glycine)³⁺ from Co(NH₃)₅(OH₂)³⁺ and glycine has been studied recently¹². The reaction involves outer-sphere association (for which evidence has been obtained from spectral observations in the UV region) followed by its reaction by an essentially dissociative mechanism since the values of the activation parameters, ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger , are almost the same as for the water exchange¹³ and aquation by azide¹⁴ of Co(NH₃)₅(OH₂)³⁺.

2. Aquation and base hydrolysis of acido-ammine complexes.

Aquation of Co(NH₃)₅(NO₂)²⁺ occurs in aqueous nitric acid media by concurrent acid independent and

acid dependent paths the mechanisms of which appear to be S_N1 and S_N1 CA respectively¹⁵.

Much controversy existed in literature at one time regarding the exact mechanism of base hydrolysis of acido-ammine complexes. While Ingold, Nyholm and Tobe in England adduced what they believed as convincing evidences for S_N2 mechanism, the American workers Basolo, Pearson and Adamson considered on the basis of other evidences the operation of S_N1 CB mechanism. Base hydrolysis of several complexes of Co(III), Cr(III) and Rh(III) have been investigated in our laboratory and our results seem to suggest that the exact mechanism depends on the nature of the central metal ion, the group being displaced and other groups present. In the case of Co(NH₃)₅(S₂O₃)⁺ it has been observed¹⁶ that the rate of replacement of S₂O₃²⁻ by various reagents such as OH⁻, Cl⁻, NH₃ shows a first order dependence on reagent concentration (this is presumably also true of H₂O) and the observed reactivity order of the different reagents is OH⁻ > Cl⁻ > NH₃ > OH₂. This supports S_N2 mechanism and rules out S_N1 CB mechanism. Again, the observed trend in ΔS^\ddagger values for the different reagents, R (OH⁻ > H₂O > Cl⁻ > NH₃) is also justified by a process in which formation of Co(III)-R bond and rupture of Co(III)-S₂O₃ bond are both important in the transition state. The trend in ΔH^\ddagger values is similar to that of the ΔS^\ddagger values, and the ΔH^\ddagger value for the reaction with NH₃ is a little over 7 kcal mole⁻¹ less than that for the reaction with water in keeping with the well-known fact that the Co(III)-NH₃ bond is stronger (thermodynamically) than the Co(III)-OH₂ bond. This again agrees with an S_N2 process in which Co(III)-R bond formation is important in the transition state (simultaneously with Co(III)-S₂O₃ bond rupture).

For base hydrolysis of Co(NH₃)₅X²⁺ (X⁻ = Cl⁻, Br⁻, N₃⁻, NO₂⁻, NCS⁻) arguments have been put forth in favour of S_N1 IP mechanism for X⁻ = Cl⁻, Br⁻, N₃⁻ and S_N2 IP mechanism for X⁻ = NO₂⁻, NCS⁻ to explain adequately the observed variation and magnitude of the enthalpy of activation ΔH^\ddagger , with change in Dq value of the complexes. The S_N1 CB mechanism does not appear to be satisfactory in any of these cases¹⁷.

For the base hydrolysis of Co(CN)₅(S₂O₃)⁴⁻, which occurs by OH⁻ independent path only, results are in agreement with a dissociation mechanism (S_N1)¹⁸.

Base hydrolysis of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NCS})^{2+}$ occurs by concurrent OH^- independent (aquation) and OH^- dependent paths¹⁹. Although the greater inertness of $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NCS})^{2+}$ (ref. 17) compared to $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{2+}$ ($\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-$) is essentially due to the entropy factor, in case of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NCS})^{2+}$ its greater inertness compared to that of the halogeno complexes is chiefly due to the enthalpy factor. This observed difference is consistent with a mechanism in which bond breaking is primarily important in the transition state in case of $\text{Cr}(\text{III})$ complex suggesting $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ IP path¹⁹ ($\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ IP path for $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NCS})^{2+}$; ref. 17).

In contrast, the base hydrolysis of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{N}_3)^{2+}$ occurs²⁰ through OH^- independent (aquation) and OH^- dependent paths, the latter involving $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ CB mechanism which only explains the observed magnitude of ΔS^\ddagger . It has been suggested further that both $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ CB and $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ IP are the limiting cases of the same general mechanism and depend on the position of H^+ in the system $\text{M}^{m+} - \text{NH}_2 - \dots - \text{H}^+ - \dots - \text{OH}^-$, which again depends on the nature of the other ligands present in the substrate which tend to influence the acidity of the ammine proton. The difference in behaviour of the isothiocyanato and azido complexes have thus been accounted for, since NCS^- is a better donor than N_3^- .

Aquation of $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{N}_3)^{2+}$ has also been studied²⁰. The reaction occurs by concurrent acid independent (path I) and acid dependent paths (path II). Magnitude of ΔS^\ddagger values agrees with $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ mechanism for path I and reaction of conjugate acid form of the complex by dissociation mechanism for path II, in which $\text{Cr}(\text{III})-\text{N}_3\text{H}$ bond breaking is synchronous with $\text{Cr}(\text{III})-\text{OH}_2$ bond formation.

Replacement of NO_2^- in $\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{ONO})^{2+}$ by OH^- has been found to occur by a pseudo-substitution process without $\text{Cr}-\text{O}$ bond rupture¹⁹. Replacement of NO_2^- in the complex by acetate in acetic acid-acetate buffer media has also been studied and probable mechanism has been discussed¹⁹.

Base hydrolysis of $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{NCS})^{2+}$ has also been studied recently²¹. The observed first order dependence of the rate on OH^- concentration is in agreement with various mechanisms. Based on considerations of the magnitude of crystal field activation energy, dependence of ΔH^\ddagger for reactions of several $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{2+}$ ($\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-, \text{N}_3^-, \text{NCS}^-$) on the Dq value of the complex, and decrease in ΔS^\ddagger with increase in solvation of X^- being released the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ IP mechanism appears probable in which both

$\text{Rh}(\text{III})-\text{OH}_2$ bond formation and $\text{Rh}(\text{III})-\text{X}$ bond dissociation (assisted by solvation of the X^- being released) are important in the transition state having a coordination number 7 of trapezoidal octahedral geometry in the transformation of the ion-pair $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{X}^{2+}$. OH^- to the ion-pair $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH}_2)^{3+}$. OH^- , which then changes to the product $\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{OH})^{2+}$ in a fast acid-base reaction. From electrostatic considerations, due to interaction between the incoming and leaving groups in the transition state of trapezoidal octahedral structure H_2O is more likely to act as the attacking nucleophile compared to OH^- .

3. Replacement of mono- and bi-dentate ligands by EDTA.

Reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3^{3+}$, $\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3^{3+}$, $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{Ox})_3^{3-}$ with EDTA in alkaline media involve complex mechanisms in which opening of a chelate ring appears rate-determining²²⁻²⁴. In the reaction of RhCl_6^{3-} with EDTA in 1-2 M NaCl at a pH ca. 2.6-3.5, the results indicate outer-sphere complex formation by RhCl_6^{3-} with H_2Y^{2-} and H_3Y^- ($\text{H}_4\text{Y} = \text{EDTA}$) followed by their transformations by dissociation and displacement mechanisms respectively²⁵.

4. Dissociation of metal chelates: Electrophilic and nucleophilic catalysis.

Dissociation of metal chelates is catalysed both by electrophiles and nucleophiles. Electrophiles such as metal ions and H^+ catalyse such reactions by fixing at the released end of the chelate group and thus preventing the ring closure back reaction. Electrophiles such as H_2O , OH^- , halide ion, etc. (i.e., good ligands) also catalyse the dissociation by fixing at the coordination site of the metal being vacated due to opening up of the chelate ring in the dissociation process and thus preventing the ring closure back reaction. In favourable cases such as with complexes of biguanide (BigH), acetylacetonate (acac), oxalate, malonate, etc., protonation of the bound ligand prior to ring opening can occur and in fact this protonation of the bound ligand facilitates its one-ended dissociation and ultimate loss²⁶⁻²⁴. In support of this it has been observed²⁷ that both for $\text{Cr}(\text{III})$ and $\text{Co}(\text{III})$ and for any particular series (tris- or bis-) of complexes of biguanide and substituted biguanides the rate decreases in the following sequence of the ligands which is also the order of decreasing basicity of the ligands and decreasing stability of the complexes: Biguanide n -Hexylbiguanide Phenylbiguanide . Again, although ethylenediamine (which is also

N, N-type ligand like biguanide) forms much less stable complexes with Cr(III) and Co(III) compared to biguanide, the ethylenediamine complexes are much more inert than the biguanide complexes and it has been observed that Co(en)_3^{3+} suffers no dissociation in 1M HClO_4 even in 2 months at ca. 30°C . This greater inertness of complexes of ethylenediamine is evidently due to inability of the bound ligand to be protonated without prior opening of the chelate ring. Thus the driving force available for ring opening in case of the biguanide complexes is absent here. Hence, while for Cr(BigH)_3^{3+} the ΔH^\ddagger value is 10.1 kcal mole $^{-1}$, the corresponding value³⁵ for Cr(en)_3^{3+} is 24.3 kcal mole $^{-1}$.

The dissociation of the biguanide ligands from $\text{Cr(BigH)}_2(\text{Ox})^+$ in acid medium occurs in stages, the second step (loss of the second biguanide ligand) being very much slower than the first step under comparable conditions³¹. Both steps are first order with respect to acid concentration. The ΔH^\ddagger values for the two steps are very close to the corresponding value for the dissociation of a biguanide ligand²⁷ from $\text{Cr(BigH)}_2(\text{OH}_2)_2^{3+}$. This near independence of ΔH^\ddagger value on the overall charge of the complex suggests that bond breaking and bond formation are both of comparable importance in the transition state in all these reactions and the mechanism thus appears to be S_N2 CA.'

Evidence for specific solvent participation in the acid catalysed dissociation of metal chelates such as $\text{Cr(OH}_2)_4(\text{OX})^+$, $\text{Cr(OH}_2)_4(\text{Mal})^+$ and Rh(BigH)_3^{3+} in fairly strong HClO_4 media has been obtained from observations on the dependence of rate on various acidity functions. In the case of the oxalato and the malonato complexes of chromium(III) mentioned above different mechanisms have been found to operate³² in different regions of acid concentration (1-9 M). In the case of Rh(BigH)_3^{3+} the mechanism appears to be S_N1 CA in the entire range of acid concentration investigated (0.8-3 M)³³.

Dissociation of Pd(BigH)_2^{2+} and of Pt(Ox)_2^{2-} in acid media containing halide ions has been studied recently and in these cases we have both catalysis by H^+ and halide ions. In the case of the palladium(II) complex³⁶ the intermediate monobiguanide complex has also been isolated and its dissociation into PdCl_4^{2-} in chloride media has been followed. In the case of the platinum(II) complex³⁷ the second step occurs very much faster owing to the high trans-effect of the halide in the intermediate Pt(Ox)_2^{2-} ($\text{X}^- = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-$). The dissociation of Pd(Ox)_2^{2-} is

however too fast to be measurable by conventional techniques. Plausible reaction mechanisms have been suggested in each of these cases.

5. Electron transfer reactions.

The reduction of ReOCl_5^{2-} by Sn(II) in HCl media forming Re(OH)Cl_5^{2-} has been studied³⁸. The mechanism is an inner-sphere atom transfer process involving ReOCl_5^{2-} and H_2SnCl_4 .

In acetic acid-acetate buffer media $\text{Co(NH}_3)_5^-(\text{NO}_2)^{2+}$ is converted into Co(II) species by intramolecular electron transfer mechanism leading to the formation of $\text{Co(NH}_3)_5^{2+}$ and NO_2 as primary products¹⁵. In nitric acid media this reaction occurs concurrent with aquation (*loc. cit*).

In acid medium Co(acac)_3 undergoes decomposition by intramolecular electron transfer process³⁹. The conjugate acid form of the complex undergoes fast one-ended dissociation of a chelate ring followed by rate-determining intramolecular electron transfer forming Co(II) and Hacac· (free radical) as primary products.

Polarography of Cu(en)_2^{2+} and Cu(Gly)_2 show irreversible diffusion controlled $\text{Cu(II)} \rightarrow \text{Cu(0)}$ electroreduction at the DME in aqueous KNO_3 media. Values of $E_{1/2}$, rate of electroreduction and corresponding E_a under comparable conditions show that Cu(Gly)_2 having a lower Dq value is reduced more easily than Cu(en)_2^{2+} having a higher Dq value. A probable mechanism of electron transfer has been suggested which explains this observation⁴⁰. Similar investigations have been completed on Ni(en)_2^{2+} and Ni(Gly)_2^{2-} both of which are reduced irreversibly while Ni(BigH)_2^{2+} undergoes reversible two electron reduction. The mechanism of electron transfer has been discussed⁴¹. Similar studies on several other complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) are now in progress.

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